

Publicly funded Cervical Cancer Screening (Pap smear)			
Year	Number of women screened	Number of women qualified for the screening	% population coverage
2014	2 212 647	9 906 366	22.34
2015	2 148 973	9 894 022	21.72
2016	2 028 217	9 896 007	20.5
2017	1 846 369	9 855 788	18.73
2018	1 689 552	9 874 141	17.11
2019	1 614 045	9 953 205	16.22
2020	1 380 428	9 977 646	13.84
2021	1 267 119	10 058 829	12.6

Publicly funded Breast Cancer Screening (mammography)			
Year	Number of women screened	Number of women qualified for the screening	% population coverage
2014	2 389 269	5 337 265	44.77
2015	2 381 783	5 404 594	44.07
2016	2 216 284	5 428 880	40.82
2017	2 130 917	5 408 693	39.4
2018	2 115 563	5 388 322	39.26
2019	2 106 696	5 378 044	39.17
2020	1 848 381	5 352 470	34.53
2021	1 883 154	5 332 698	35.31